

PHARMACOVIGILANCE STUDIES ON ANTIDIABETIC MEDICATIONS

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1)ABSTRACT: Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a significant global health issue, particularly Type 2 DM, which is exacerbated by lifestyle factors like obesity and physical inactivity. The study aims to assess the prescription patterns, common adverse drug reactions among diabetic patients, especially those receiving multiple medications, to better understand their health challenges. A retrospective observational study was conducted over three months by survey. Data were collected through data collection form it contains demographics, treatment regimens, comorbidities, and adverse drug reactions was gathered using structured questionnaires and analysed using descriptive statistics.

KEYWORDS: DM-Diabetes mellitus, ADR-Adverse drug reaction, WHO-World health organization, ADE-Adverse drug event, FDA-Food and drug administration.

2)INTRODUCTION:

DIABETES MELLITUS

Diabetes mellitus is defined as a heterogeneous metabolic disorder characterized by a common feature of chronic hyperglycemia with disturbance of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism. DM is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality world over and approximately 1% of the population suffers from diabetes mellitus. [1]

CLASSIFICATION AND ETIOLOGY:

TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS (10%): (Earlier called insulin dependent or juvenile-onset diabetes)

TYPE 1A DM: Immune mediated

TYPE 1B DM: idiopathic

TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS (80%): (Earlier called non-insulin dependent or maturity-onset diabetes mellitus) [1]

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL STATISTICS

The international diabetes federation estimates that around 77 million people in India are suffering from diabetes mellitus with projections suggesting it could rise to 134 million by 2045. Type 2 diabetes mellitus accounts for 90-95% of all cases leading to blindness, kidney failure, amputations and cardiovascular diseases.

Prevalence: Around 463 million people worldwide have diabetes, with the highest prevalence in western Pacific region, followed by Southeast Asia and Europe.

Incidence: Diabetes incidence is increasing globally, with 4.2 million cases caused in 2021, making it the eighth leading healthcare access.

Age and gender: Diabetes mellitus affects people of all ages, with 80% aged 60 or older. It affects both women face additional challenges, including increased pregnancy complications. [2]

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

The pathophysiology of diabetes mellitus differs significantly between type 1 and type 2 diabetes.

Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus:

Autoimmune Destruction: T1DM is an autoimmune disease characterized by the destruction of pancreatic beta cells in the islets of Langerhans, often triggered by genetic predisposition and environmental triggers.

Metabolic Effects: Insulin deficiency leads to hyperglycaemia, polyuria, polydipsia, weight loss, and ketogenesis, potentially causing diabetic ketoacidosis.

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus:

Insulin Resistance: T2DM is a condition characterized by insulin resistance, affecting liver, muscle, and fat tissues, often linked to obesity, sedentary lifestyle, and genetic factors.

Impaired Insulin Secretion: Over time, the pancreas cannot produce enough insulin to overcome this resistance, resulting in relative insulin deficiency.

Incretin Effect: In T2DM, there is often a diminished incretin effect, where hormones like GLP-1 that enhance insulin secretion are less effective.

Metabolic Dysfunction: Insulin resistance and impaired secretion lead to elevated blood glucose levels, causing potential complications like cardiovascular disease, nephropathy, neuropathy, and retinopathy over time.[1]

Complications :

Acute complications: Diabetic Ketoacidosis, Diabetic hyperosmolar nonketotic syndrome, Hypoglycemia.

Chronic complications: Microvascular, Retinopathy, Nephropathy, Neuropathy, Diabetic foot, Dermopathy, Macrovascular, Cerebrovascular, Cardiovascular, Peripheral vascular disease.[3]

TREATMENT:

1)INSULIN

Types of insulin : Rapid-acting insulin, Short-acting insulin, Intermediate-acting insulin, Long-acting insulin.

2)ORAL ANTIDIABETIC DRUGS:

Insulin injections are the main drawback, while oral active drugs lower blood glucose levels in diabetics and are effective orally. Common oral antidiabetic drugs include:

a)Sulfonyl ureases: Examples: Glyburide , Glipizide (Glucotrol), Glimepiride (Amaryl)

b)Biguanides: Examples: Metformin(Glucophage)

c)Thiazolidinediones(TZDs): Examples: Pioglitazone (Actos)

d)DPP-4 Inhibitors: Examples: Sitagliptin (Januvia), Sitagliptin (Onglaze)

e)SGLT-2 Inhibitors: Examples: Canagliflozin (Invokana), Dapagliflozin (Farfiga), Empagliflozin (Jardiance)[4]

ADVERSE DRUG REACTION:

According to WHO (World health organization), **pharmacovigilance** is defined as: "The science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse effects or any other drug-related problems".

Pharmacovigilance(pv) can be categorized into various types based on its focus and methodology,here are the main types

- 1) Passive Surveillance
- 2) Active Surveillance
- 3) Targeted Spontaneous Reporting (TSR)
- 4) Comparative Observational Studies
- 5) Clinical Trial Pharmacovigilance
- 6) Epidemiological studies
- 7) Signal Detection & Evaluation[5]

The WHO defines an adverse drug reaction(ADR) as ‘Any response to a drug which is noxious and unintended,and which occurs at doses normally used in man for prophylaxis ,diagnosis ,therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological function’. [6]

Adverse drug reactions can be classified into five types depending on:-

Depending on Onset of Event: Acute (<60 minutes), Sub-acute (1-24 hours), latent (> 2 days)

Based on Type Of Reactions: i) Rawlins and Thompson classification (1991): Type A (Augmented Reactions), Type B (bizarre reactions), Type C (chronic reactions), Type D (Delayed type reactions). Type E (end of treatment). ii) Wills and Brown Classification: stipe A (Augmented Reactions), Type B (bizarre reactions). +Type C (chronic/Chemical reactions), Type D (Delayed type reactions), Type E (end of treatment), Type F (Familial reactions). Type G (Genotoxicity), Type H (Hypersensitivity), Type U (Unclassified).

Based on Severity: Minor, Moderate, Severe, Lethal.

Depending on Whether They Could Take Place in Any Patient, or in a Specific Susceptible.[7]

Assessment of ADRs:

Severity assessment scales:

- 1) Hartwig and Siegel Severity Assessment Scale
- 2) Schumock and Thornton Preventability Scale[8]

Other assessment methods:

- 1) WHO-UMC Causality Assessment Scale
- 2) Naranjo Algorithm (Scale)
- 3) Kramer’s Scale
- 4) Jones' Scale
- 5) French Immutability Method[9]

3) MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN:

Retrospective Observational study

STUDY PERIOD:

Study was carried out for a period of 3 months.

SOURCES OF DATA COLLECTION:

- 1) From patients and patient caregiver's interview
- 2) Patients' prescriptions
- 3) Laboratory investigation data reports

STUDY CRITERIA:

Inclusion criteria:

- 1) Diabetes mellitus patients of all age groups
- 2) Both male and females
- 3) Patient with or without comorbid conditions

Exclusion criteria:

- 1) Pregnant women and psychiatry patients
- 2) Patients who are not willing to participate

SAMPLE SIZE CALCULATION:

The sample size was calculated based on the average number of patients visiting the study site. To represent 3-month patient population of 143, the sample size is calculated using the below formula.

Sample size for infinite population

$$= \frac{Z^2 \times p \times (1-p)}{c^2} = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times (1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = 108$$

Where, p- Proportion of population

C- Confidence interval

Z- Value represents the probability that a sample will fall within a certain distribution Sample size for finite population: New sample size =108

STUDY PROCEDURE:

A 3 month retrospective study was conducted through a survey, An informed consent form was given to the patients, A comprehensive patient data collection form was developed to capture essential details like patient demographics, patient history, comorbid conditions, adverse drug reactions and the drug treatment.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

The analysis focused on various aspects of prescription patterns, including patient demographics, type of diabetes, duration, family history, other complications, adverse effects, medications. The data obtained directly from patient survey using google forms and then sorted, cleaned in microsoft excel, qualitative variables were reported in percentage and in graphical representation while quantitative variables were summarized using pearson chi square test formula

4) RESULTS**A) GENDER DISTRIBUTION:**

The gender breakdown of the population reveals a nearly even split between males and females. Out of a total of 143 individuals, 73 males and 70 females were recorded with no transgenders.

GENDER	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
MALE	73	51.05
FEMALE	70	48.95
OTHERS	0	0.00

GENDER-WISE DISTRIBUTION**B) AGE DISTRIBUTION:**

The data shows a diverse age distribution among 143 individuals, with nearly 70 patients (48.95%) falling within the 41-60 age range. This suggests a balance between professional and personal lives, with younger individuals underrepresented. The 21-40 age range represents 40 patients (27.97%), likely in the early to middle stages of their careers. Lastly, individuals over the age of 60 make up 25 patients (17.48%) of the group suggesting a moderate representation of older adults. This data could help understand the group's priorities, behaviors, and decision-making processes.

AGE	NO.OF PATIENTS (N=143)	PERCENTAGE(%)
0-20	8	5.5
21-40	40	27.97
41-60	70	48.96
>60	25	17.48

AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION

C) FAMILY HISTORY DISTRIBUTION:

The data shows a notable difference in the family history of diabetes among the population. Out of a total of 143 individuals, 80 individuals (or about **55.9%**) reported having a family history of diabetes, while 63 individuals (or **44.1%**) did not.

FAMILY HISTORY	NO. OF PATIENTS (N=143)	PERCENTAGE (%)
YES	80	55.94
NO	63	44.06

FAMILY HISTORY DISTRIBUTION

D) DISTRIBUTION OF OCCUPATIONS:

The occupational background of 143 patients reveals a diverse range of professions. Housekeepers have the largest number with 42 patients, possibly due to work stress or physical demands. Teachers have the great numbers with 25 patients, possibly due to their focus on education or health challenges. Business and students have the lowest with 13 patients, possibly representing younger individuals or high-stress careers. The "Others" category has the largest number with 11 students and the other people with work category as tailors, carpenters, taxi drivers, industrial workers, auto drivers, bus drivers, engineers are also contributed during the survey showcasing the diverse occupations within the population.

OCCUPATION TYPE	NO OF PATIENTS (N=143)	PERCENTAGE (%)
HOUSE KEEPERS	42	29.4
BUSINESS	13	9.1
TEACHERS	25	17.5
STUDENTS	13	9.1
OTHERS	50	34.9

DISTRIBUTION OF OCCUPATION**E) TYPE OF DIABETES:**

The data reveals a significant predominance of Type 2 diabetes in the population, with 131 individuals (or approximately 91.7%) diagnosed with this form of diabetes. In contrast, Type 1 diabetes is much less common, affecting only 12 individuals (or about 8.3%) of the population.

TYPE OF DIABETES	NO. OF PATIENTS (N=143)	PERCENTAGE (%)
TYPE-1	12	8.4
TYPE-2	131	91.6

DISTRIBUTION OF TYPES OF DIABETES MELLITUS

F) DURATION DISTRIBUTION:

The duration of diabetes varied significantly among the patients. 15 patients were diagnosed within the past 0-1 year, while 74 patients had been living with diabetes for 1-5 years. 29 patients had diabetes for 5-10 years, and 25 patients had been managing the condition for more than 10 years. This distribution highlights a broad range of diabetes progression among the patients.

DURATION OF DIABETES	NO OF PATIENTS (N=143)
PAST 0-1 YEARS	15
PAST 1-5 YEARS	74
PAST 5-10 YEARS	29
MORE THAN 10 YEARS	25

DURATION DISTRIBUTION

F) DISTRIBUTION OF ANY OTHER COMORBID CONDITIONS:

These are the main distribution of comorbid condition , highlighting the various health issues, hypertension is the most common condition.

DISTRIBUTION OF ANY OTHER COMORBID CONDITIONS

COMORBID CONDITON FREQUENCY		PERCENTAGE(%)
HYPERTENSION	30	31.9
GASTRITIS	17	18.1
GOUT	10	10.6
HYPERLIPIDEMIA	9	9.6
ARTHRITIS	4	4.3
HYPERTHYROIDISM	4	4.3
OTHERS	20	21.3

DISTRIBUTION OF OTHER COMORBID CONDITIONS

G) PATIENT RELATED FACTOR DISTRIBUTION :

The study reveals an even distribution of patients who engage in physical activity, with a majority following a Proper Diet. However, a significant portion still doesn't, potentially affecting their health. The majority of patients take their medications regularly, indicating adherence to treatment plans. However, a significant portion don't, indicating a need for improved patient education or access to monitoring tools. Additionally, most patients report unpleasant side effects, suggesting potential improvements in patient comfort to treatment.

PATIENT RELATED FACTOR DISTRIBUTION	YES NO	
	DOES A PATIENT DO ANY PHYSICALL ACTIVITY ?	72
DOES A PETIENT FOLLOW A PROPER DIET ?	91	52
DOES A PERSON TAKE MEDICATIONS REGULARLY ?	137	6

DOES A PERSON CHECK GLUCOSE LEVEL REGULARLY ?	97	46
DOES A PERSON FEEL ANY UNPLEASANT SIDE EFFECTS?	103	40

DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENT RELATED FACTORS

H) POSSIBLE ADVERSE EFFECTS DISTRIBUTION

- **Nausea, Headache, and Diarrhea** are the most commonly reported side effects, affecting **45 patients**.
- **Acidity and Heartburn** are also quite common, affecting **36 patients**.
- **Lactic Acidosis** and **Ketoacidosis** are both rare but serious conditions, with **11** and **1** patients affected, respectively.
- **Fatigue, Dizziness** and **Loss of Appetite** are also notable but less frequent than nausea and acidity.

This table provides a clear overview of the distribution of side effects among the patient population, highlighting the most and least common adverse effects.

POSSIBLE ADVERSE EFFECTS SEEN	FREQUENCY
FATIGUE, DIZZINESS	30
BODY PAIN, MUSCLE CRAMPING	20
ACIDITY, HEART BURN	36
LOSS OF APETITE	25
LACTIC ACIDOSIS	11
KETO ACIDOSIS	1
VITAMIN B12 DEFICIENCY	21
HYPOGLYCEMIA	7
LIVER DYSFUNCTION	1
NAUSEA, HEADACHE,DIARRHOEA	45

POSSIBLE ADVERSE EFFECT DISTRIBUTION

I) DISTRIBUTION OF DRUGS WITH ITS COMPOSITION:

Metformin is the most commonly prescribed drug for managing type 2 diabetes, working by decreasing glucose production in the liver and improving insulin sensitivity in muscle cells. Combinations of Metformin with Glimpiride, Voglibose, Pioglitazone, and other agents can provide a comprehensive approach to controlling blood glucose levels. Metformin with Glipizide enhances insulin release from the pancreas, while Metformin decreases glucose production in the liver. Metformin with Teneligliptin prevents the breakdown of incretin hormones, enhancing insulin secretion while controlling hepatic glucose output. Metformin with Repaglinide is used for postprandial glucose control. Insulin-based regimens include Insulin+ Metformin, insulin monotherapy, and Metformin Hydrochloride. Other drug options include Glimpiride, Glipizide, Ertugliflozin, and other medications. Metformin Hydrochloride remains the first-line treatment due to its effectiveness, safety, and minimal risk of hypoglycemia. Other drugs include Ertugliflozin, which reduces glucose reabsorption in the kidneys, Ertugliflozin, and others.

DRUG COMPOSITION	FREQUENCY
METFORMIN + GLIMPRIDE	11
METFORMIN +GLIMEPRIDE+VOGLIBOSE	5
METFORMIN + GLIMEPRIDE + PIOGLITAZONE	6
METFORMIN + GLIPIZIDE	4
METFORMIN + TENELIGLIPTIN	3
METFORMIN + REPAGLINIDE	3
METFORMIN + VILDAGLIPTIN	2
INSULIN + METFORMIN	15
METFORMIN HYDROCHLORIDE	60
GLIMEPRIDE	5
GLIPIZIDE	4

ERTOGLIFLOCIN	2
INSULIN	6
OTHERS	17

DRUG NAMES WITH ITS COMPOSITION

J) DRUG – DRUG INTERACTIONS:

Drug-drug interactions can significantly affect the effectiveness and safety of medications, often requiring close monitoring or dosage adjustments. For instance, the combination of Olmesartan and insulin regular human can lead to an increased insulin effect, though the exact mechanism of this interaction is unclear. This may necessitate adjustments to insulin dosage and more frequent glucose monitoring. Similarly, Metformin and Nifedipine have a minor interaction where Nifedipine increases the absorption of Metformin in the gastrointestinal tract, potentially affecting blood glucose control.

DRUG - DRUG SEVERITY	MECHANISM OF INTERACTION ACTION	MONITOR	
Olmesartan + insulin regular human	Monitor closely	Olmesartan increases effect of insulin regular human by unspecified interaction mechanism	Concomitant use of insulin and ARBs may require insulin dosage adjustment and increase glucose monitoring
Metformin + nifedipine	Minor	Nifedipine increases levels of metformin by enhancing GI absorption. Applies only oral forms of agents	Closely observed for loss of blood glucose control, when drugs are withdrawn from patient

Amlodipine +metformin	Monitor closely	Amlodipine decreases effect of metformin by pharmacodynamic antagonism	Closely observed for loss of blood glucose control, when drugs are withdrawn from patient
Metformin + furosemide	Minor	Metformin decreases levels of furosemide by unspecified interaction mechanism	Closely observed for loss of blood glucose control, when drugs are withdrawn from patient
Metformin + insulin regular human	Monitor closely	Metformin , Insulin regular human either increases effects of the other by pharmacodynamic	Antidiabetic agents are often used in combination dose adjustment
		synergism	may required when initiating or discontinued
Ibuprofen + glimepiride	Monitor closely	Ibuprofen increases effect of glimepiride	Risk of hypoglycemia

J) DISTRIBUTION OF DRUGS:

Most patients, 97 out of 143, received monotherapy, a single drug used to manage diabetes, like Metformin. This approach is preferred in early stages or when blood glucose control is manageable. Polytherapy, the use of multiple drugs, was prescribed to 46 patients, often used in advanced diabetes patients or those requiring more intensive management.

DRUGS	NO. OF PATIENTS (N=143)	PERCENTAGE(%)
MONOTHERAPY	97	67.8
POLYTHERAPY	46	32.2

DISTRIBUTION OF DRUGS

K) DISTRIBUTION OF MONOTHERAPY DRUGS:

Out of **97 patients** prescribed monotherapy, **60** were given **Biguanides** (primarily Metformin), the most common first-line treatment for type 2 diabetes. **21 patients** received **Insulin** as monotherapy, often used for more advanced cases or type 1 diabetes. Additionally, **13 patients** were prescribed **other oral hypoglycemic agents**, including drugs like **Sulfonylureas**, **DPP-4 inhibitors**, or **SGLT2 inhibitors**, as alternatives or

second-line treatments. This shows that while Metformin is the most frequently used, other options are considered based on patient needs.

DRUGS USED AS MONOTHERAPY	NO. OF PATIENTS (N=97)	PERCENTAGE(%)
BIGUANIDES	60	61.9
INSULIN	21	21.7
OTHER ORAL HYPO-GLYCEMIC AGENTS	13	13.4

DISTRIBUTION OF MONOTHERAPY DRUGS

L) DISTRIBUTION OF MEDICATIONS FOR COMORBID CONDITIONS:

In addition to diabetes-specific treatments, several other medications were prescribed to manage related health conditions in patients. **32 patients** received **antihypertensive drugs** to control high blood pressure, while **15 patients** were treated with **antihyperlipidemic agents** to manage elevated cholesterol levels. **10 patients** were prescribed **anti-gout therapy** to address gout-related issues, and **30 patients** were given **proton pump inhibitors** to manage acid reflux or related gastrointestinal conditions. Additionally, **20 patients** received other medications for various health concerns like anti arrhythmic drugs, anti-asthmatic drugs, diuretics, antibiotics and others.

OTHER MEDICATIONS	NO OF PATIENTS
Antihypertensive drugs	32
Antihyperlipidemic agents	15
Anti gout therapy	10
Proton pump inhibitors	30
Others	20

DISTRIBUTION OF OTHER MEDICATIONS

M)CORRELATION THERAPY AND ADRs:

The analysis focused on various aspects including patient demographics, type of diabetes, duration, family history, patient related factor between, other complications. The study found a significant correlation between therapy type and adverse drug reactions (ADRs), with a significance p-value of 0.011, less than the 0.05 threshold. Patients undergoing polytherapy had a higher risk of ADRs, with all 40 patients reporting them, while monotherapy patients had a lower risk. The results suggest that the complexity of therapy may influence ADR risk.

THERAPY	AD _R s		TOTAL	SIGNIFICANCE
	YES	NO		
MONOTHERAPY	88	15	103	0.011
POLYTHERAPY	40	0	40	
TOTAL	128	15	143	

< 0.05 = Significance

5)DISCUSSION :

A) Socio-demographic characteristics and comorbidities

In this study the majority of patients were 73 males (51%) and 70 females (49%) and most patients (48.95%) were between 41 and 60 years old, This distribution aligns with a previous studies such as Singh H *et al.*, [10] Similar balance with, 79 females (51.29%) and 75 males (48.7%) were between under 35 years with 84 patients (54.55%) and over 35 years with 70 patients (45.45%). Furthermore, comorbidities in our survey includes Hypertension (30), Gastritis (17), and Gout (10) were common and Hypertension (30), Gastritis (17), and Gout (10) were common comorbidities in **Kumar BN *et al*** [10] survey.

B) Drug prescription pattern

The study observed a predominant use of oral hypo-glycaemic agents include Metformin combined with various agents like Glipizide, Teneligliptin, Voglibose, and Repaglinide and parenteral like insulin were administered. Out of 143 ,97 patients prescribed monotherapy, 60 were given Biguanides (primarily Metformin), the most common first-line treatment for type 2 diabetes. 21 patients received Insulin as monotherapy, often used for more advanced cases or type 1 diabetes. which is compared with other studies like **Joung KI *et al.***, [11] uses like newer diabetes treatments like SGLT2 inhibitors, GLP-1RAs, and TZDs, metformin and insulin. This suggests that while Metformin remains a cornerstone therapy in diabetes management, newer drugs bring specific risks, especially for women. The findings suggest a need for close monitoring of adverse events, particularly when using medications like SGLT2 inhibitors and TZDs, which introduce gender- specific challenges.

C) Adverse effect discussion

Metformin remains a dominant treatment, but newer classes like SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP1RAs are associated with specific ADR patterns, especially in women. Gender-specific differences in ADRs, The ADRs like Nausea, Headache, and Diarrhoea are the most commonly reported side effects, affecting 45 patients. Acidity and Heartburn are also quite common, affecting 36 patients. Lactic Acidosis and Ketoacidosis are both rare but serious conditions, with 11 and 1 patients affected, respectively. Fatigue, Dizziness and Loss of Appetite are also notable which is compared with the other studies like **Singh H *et al.***, [10] this includes Gastrointestinal disorders: for 61 patients (39.61%) Skin disorders for 44 patients (28.57%) Respiratory disorders: for 17 patients (11.03%) CNS and neurological disorders: for 13 patients (8.44%). This suggests a significant link between polypharmacy and gastrointestinal conditions in this cohort.

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Date:

Place:

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